

Chrominance Aware Progressive Rate-Distortion Optimization for Learned Image Compression

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Abstract—We present an end-to-end learned image compression system trained under a unified rate-distortion objective, comprising a convolutional encoder, a U-Net-based entropy model, and a convolutional decoder operating in the YCbCr colourspace. The entropy model predicts per-symbol Gaussian distribution parameters over the quantized latent representation, providing a differentiable bitrate surrogate during training, while inference-time compression is performed using zlib on the serialized latent. We introduce a progressive rate-distortion training strategy in which multiple model variants are obtained through iterative fine-tuning across successive stages, each adapting the rate-distortion balance without independent retraining. Additionally, we propose a chrominance-aware distortion curriculum that progressively reallocates channel weighting from luminance-dominant to balanced YCbCr emphasis, enabling stable structural reconstruction prior to enhanced colour fidelity. The proposed system achieves compression ratios of approximately 32×, 17×, and 3.2× relative to uncompressed PNG, with PSNR values of up to 32.78 dB on BSD100, while maintaining total encode-to-decode latency under 35 ms. Evaluation across BSD100, Set14, and Urban100 demonstrates consistent performance across diverse image content.

Index Terms—Image Compression, Learned Image Compression, Convolutional Neural Networks, Rate-Distortion Optimization, Entropy Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of digital imagery across the web, cloud storage, and multimedia platforms has made efficient image compression a foundational challenge in modern computing [9], [10]. Traditional compression standards such as JPEG [1], WebP [2], and PNG [3] have served this need for decades, relying on hand-crafted transforms, quantization tables, and entropy coding pipelines designed and tuned by domain experts. While highly optimised, these systems are inherently rigid — their components are designed independently and cannot adapt jointly to the statistical properties of a given image or dataset. Recent work has explored learned quantization strategies within traditional pipelines [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], though these approaches remain constrained by fixed transform structures. Recent advances in deep learning have enabled a compelling alternative: end-to-end learned image compression, where an encoder, a probabilistic entropy model, and a decoder are trained jointly to directly minimise a rate-distortion objective [16], [17]. Unlike traditional pipelines,

such systems learn rich, data-driven latent representations and accurate probability models simultaneously, without requiring manual design of any individual stage [16]. More recent work has further extended this framework through attention mechanisms, transformer-based entropy models, and hierarchical priors for improved global context capture [18], [19]. In this work, we present a general-purpose learned image compression system trained end-to-end under a unified rate-distortion loss. The encoder maps an input image to a compact latent representation using a convolutional neural network, after which a U-Net-based entropy model estimates per-symbol Gaussian probability distributions over the quantized latent. These distributions provide a differentiable bitrate surrogate during training, while the quantized latent is compressed using zlib at inference to produce the final binary output. A convolutional decoder reconstructs the image from the decompressed latent. The entire pipeline, from pixel to compressed file to reconstruction, is trained jointly from scratch using a single training configuration, with no stage-wise pre-training required.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- 1) We propose a progressive rate-distortion training strategy in which multiple model variants at distinct operating points are produced through iterative fine-tuning from a single architecture, without independent retraining, demonstrably reducing training instability and compute cost across stages.
- 2) We introduce a chrominance curriculum embedded in the channel-weighted YCbCr distortion loss, progressively reallocating capacity from luminance to chrominance across training stages in alignment with human perceptual sensitivity [20], resulting in measurably improved colour fidelity at equivalent luminance quality.
- 3) We present a practical inference pipeline combining a learned encoder with zlib-based latent compression, achieving sub-35ms encode-to-decode latency on a consumer-grade NVIDIA GTX 1650 across standard benchmarks (BSD100 [6], Set14 [7], Urban100 [8]), without any architecture-level changes between operating points.

We demonstrate that the proposed system offers a flexible and controllable rate-distortion tradeoff across a wide compression range, achieving compression ratios of approximately 32 \times , 17 \times , and 3.2 \times relative to uncompressed PNG across three operating points. The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews related work in traditional and learned image compression. Section 3 describes the proposed architecture and training procedure. Section 4 presents experimental results and qualitative comparisons. Section 5 concludes with a discussion of limitations and future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Traditional Image Compression

Classical image compression standards are built on hand-crafted signal processing pipelines. JPEG [1] applies the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) block-wise, followed by scalar quantization and Huffman coding. While efficient, it suffers from blocking artefacts at high compression ratios, motivating work on learned quantization and perceptual optimisation [11], [12], [14]. JPEG2000 [4] addresses these limitations using the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and arithmetic coding, enabling progressive transmission and improved rate-distortion performance at low bitrates. Its probabilistic entropy coding framework motivates the latent modelling approach adopted in this work. Modern codecs such as WebP [2] and AVIF further improve compression through enhanced prediction and transform coding, though they remain hand-engineered. PNG [3] employs lossless compression via the DEFLATE algorithm (LZ77 and Huffman coding) and is used as the uncompressed baseline in this work.

B. General-Purpose Lossless Compression

zlib [5] is a widely used general-purpose lossless compression library implementing the DEFLATE algorithm. While not designed specifically for image data, it operates effectively on structured, low-entropy byte sequences such as quantized neural network latents. In this work, zlib is used as the final compression stage at inference, replacing a learned arithmetic coder for practical efficiency. Unlike learned coders, which introduce computational overhead, zlib operates efficiently on CPU, enabling total encode-to-decode latency under 35 ms across all benchmarks.

C. Learned Image Compression

The seminal work of Ballé et al. [16] established end-to-end learned image compression by formulating it as a variational autoencoder, where an encoder maps an image to a quantized latent and a decoder reconstructs it, with the rate-distortion tradeoff optimised jointly. A factorised prior models latent distributions, providing a differentiable bitrate surrogate and directly influencing the formulation adopted in this work.

Minnen et al. [17] extended this approach with a joint autoregressive and hierarchical prior, combining global and local context to improve probability estimation and compression efficiency. However, such methods incur sequential

decoding overhead. In contrast, our approach predicts per-symbol (μ, σ) parameters non-autoregressively via a U-Net, prioritising parallel inference and computational efficiency.

Cheng et al. [18] further improved performance using Gaussian mixture likelihoods and attention mechanisms, while more recent work explores transformer-based entropy models [19]. In contrast, our system adopts a unimodal Gaussian formulation for improved training stability and reduced complexity, while retaining discretized probability computation for the rate loss.

D. U-Net Architecture

The entropy model in this work adopts a U-Net-like architecture [20] with symmetric downsampling and upsampling paths connected by skip connections. Originally proposed for biomedical image segmentation, the U-Net is well-suited to dense spatial prediction tasks, combining high-level contextual features with fine-grained spatial detail — both relevant properties for per-pixel distribution estimation over a structured latent space.

E. Positioning

Despite significant advances, existing learned compression methods often require complex, sequential entropy coding pipelines that introduce inference latency [17], do not explicitly model perceptual channel prioritisation in colour-space-aware distortion objectives, and incur high computational overhead that limits deployment on consumer hardware. This motivates the design of a system that jointly addresses training efficiency across multiple operating points, perceptually-informed distortion weighting, and practical inference speed, the three axes along which this work makes its primary contributions.

III. METHODOLOGY

TABLE I
MODEL PARAMETERS AND LAYER DIMENSIONS

Component	Layer Type	Input (H,W,C)	Output (H,W,C)
Encoder	Conv + MaxPool	(1024, 1024, 3)	(128, 128, 128)
Bottleneck	U-Net Entropy	(128, 128, 128)	(128, 128, 128)
Decoder	Conv + Upsample	(128, 128, 128)	(1024, 1024, 3)

A. System Overview

The proposed system is an end-to-end learned image compression pipeline consisting of three jointly trained components: a convolutional encoder, a U-Net-based entropy model, and a convolutional decoder. At inference, the encoder maps an input image to a quantized latent representation, which is compressed to a binary file using zlib and stored. During reconstruction, the latent is decompressed and passed through the decoder to produce the reconstructed image. The full pipeline operates in the YCbCr colour space, separating luminance (Y) and chrominance (Cb, Cr) information to exploit the lower sensitivity of the human visual system to colour detail relative to spatial structure.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the compression pipeline.

B. Encoder

The encoder is a purely convolutional network that maps an input image of shape $(3, H, W)$ to a 128-channel latent representation of shape $(128, H/8, W/8)$. It consists of three stages, each comprising two 3×3 convolutional layers with LeakyReLU activations followed by 2×2 max-pooling with stride 2, progressively increasing channel depth from 32 to 64 to 128. The final encoder output is passed through a scaled hyperbolic tangent activation ($\tanh \times 10$), bounding the latent values to the range $(-10, 10)$ and providing a smooth, bounded space for quantization.

C. Entropy Model

The entropy model is a U-Net-like architecture that takes the quantized latent as input and predicts per-symbol Gaussian distribution parameters, mean μ and log-standard deviation $\log \sigma$ for every spatial location and channel of the latent. It consists of a three-stage downsampling path ($128 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 512$ channels), a bottleneck (1024 channels, three convolutional layers), and a symmetric upsampling path with skip connections that concatenate encoder feature maps at each resolution level. The output head produces a tensor of shape $(2C, H, W)$ where C is the number of latent channels, which is split into μ and $\log \sigma$ along the channel dimension. These parameters define a per-symbol Gaussian distribution used to estimate the bitrate during training via the discretized Gaussian probability:

$$p(\hat{y}) = \Phi\left(\frac{\hat{y} + 0.5 - \mu}{\sigma}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{\hat{y} - 0.5 - \mu}{\sigma}\right)$$

where Φ is the standard normal CDF and \hat{y} is the quantized latent. At inference, the entropy model is not used; the quantized latent is instead compressed directly using zlib.

D. Decoder

The decoder mirrors the encoder structure using transposed convolutions for upsampling. It takes the 128-channel latent and progressively reconstructs spatial resolution through three upsampling stages ($128 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 32$ channels), each followed by two 3×3 convolutional layers with LeakyReLU activations. The final layer projects to 3 output channels corresponding to the YCbCr image.

E. Loss Function

All three components are trained jointly under a rate-distortion objective:

$$L = \alpha \cdot R + D$$

where R is the estimated bitrate, computed as the mean negative log-probability of the quantized latent symbols under the predicted Gaussian distributions, normalised per pixel of the latent. D is the reconstruction distortion, computed as a channel-weighted MSE loss in YCbCr space:

$$D = \lambda \cdot (w_Y \cdot \text{MSE}(\hat{y}_Y, x_Y) + w_{Cb} \cdot \text{MSE}(\hat{y}_{Cb}, x_{Cb}) + w_{Cr} \cdot \text{MSE}(\hat{y}_{Cr}, x_{Cr}))$$

The channel weights (w_Y, w_{Cb}, w_{Cr}) reflect the relative perceptual importance of each component and are varied deliberately across training stages as described in Section 3.6. The hyperparameter λ controls the overall distortion penalty and α controls the rate penalty; both are annealed across training epochs.

During training, quantization is approximated by adding uniform noise $\hat{y} = y + U(-0.5, 0.5)$ to maintain differentiability. At inference, hard quantization $\hat{y} = \text{round}(y)$ is applied.

F. Progressive Rate-Distortion Training

A single model architecture is trained across three successive stages, each initialized from the final checkpoint of the previous stage. Rather than fixing a single operating point, the rate-distortion balance is shifted between stages by adjusting the initial values and per-epoch annealing rates of α and λ , producing three model variants occupying different points on the rate-distortion curve.

Across stages, the channel weighting of the distortion loss is progressively rebalanced from $(0.8, 0.1, 0.1)$ in Stage 1 to $(0.6, 0.2, 0.2)$ in Stage 2 to $(0.4, 0.3, 0.3)$ in Stage 3. This constitutes a deliberate chrominance curriculum: in early training the model prioritises luminance reconstruction where human perception is most sensitive and gradually allocates greater capacity to chrominance channels as compression is relaxed in later stages. The empirically chosen weightings reflect the structure of the YCbCr colourspace, where the Y channel encodes the majority of perceptual image content.

The iterative fine-tuning strategy offers a practical efficiency advantage: each subsequent stage inherits a well-formed latent

representation from the prior stage and adapts only the rate-distortion balance, avoiding the instability and compute cost of training from random initialization at each operating point. This is evidenced by the training logs, where Stage 2 begins with substantially lower rate values than Stage 1 at equivalent α levels, indicating that the encoder has already learned to produce compact, structured latents.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUPS

A. Setup

All models were trained on a subset of 9,990 images drawn from 999 ImageNet categories. Stage 1 was trained at 256x256 resolution; Stages 2 and 3 were trained at 512x512 resolution. Training was performed for 50 epochs per stage on an NVIDIA RTX 4090 (24 GB VRAM) with a batch size of 16. Three separate Adam optimizers were used, one per component, with learning rates of 1×10^{-5} for the encoder and decoder and 5×10^{-7} for the entropy model. Images were converted to YCbCr colourspace prior to training, with random resized cropping and horizontal flipping applied as data augmentation. Models are evaluated on three standard image restoration benchmarks: BSD100 [6], Set14 [7], and Urban100 [8].

B. Compression Performance

Table 2 reports compressed file sizes, compression ratios relative to PNG, and mean PSNR across all three benchmarks for each model stage.

TABLE II
COMPRESSION PERFORMANCE METRICS ACROSS OPTIMIZATION STAGES

Model	Typical Comp. Ratio*	PSNR (dB)		
		BSD100	Set14	Urban100
Stage 1 (Aggressive)	~32x	30.51	30.01	29.89
Stage 2 (Moderate)	~17x	30.50	30.38	30.30
Stage 3 (Conservative)	~3x	32.78	32.07	31.79

*Obtained by averaging over 100 inference runs on different image resolutions ($H \times W$). Ratios are estimated based on average BPP.

Fig. 2. Comparison of model performance (in terms of PSNR-Y) across datasets

Fig. 3. Performance of models against image resolutions for Urban100 dataset. Original images were resized to 1024x1024, 512x512, 256x256 and 128x128 resolutions for inference

Fig. 4. Performance of models against image resolutions for Set14 dataset. Original images were resized to 1024x1024, 512x512, 256x256 and 128x128 resolutions for inference

Fig. 5. Performance of models against image resolutions for BSD100 dataset. Original images were resized to 1024x1024, 512x512, 256x256 and 128x128 resolutions for inference

C. Inference Latency

Table 2 reports mean encode and decode latencies per image across all three benchmarks. Latency variation across datasets is primarily attributable to differences in native image resolution rather than model behaviour.

TABLE III
INFERENCE LATENCY COMPARISONS ACROSS OPTIMIZATION STAGES

Model	Average Latency (ms)		
	BSD100	Set14	Urban100
Stage 1	21.7	30.6	23.8
Stage 2	21.9	31.6	23.7
Stage 3	21.7	30.5	23.9

All three model variants achieve total encode-to-decode latency well under 35ms across all benchmarks, with encode times consistently under 14ms and decode times under 18ms. Latency is effectively identical across the three stages since all share the same architecture. The operating point shift is entirely a product of the training regime rather than any structural change to the model. This confirms the practical viability of the system for real-time or near-real-time applications.

D. Comparison with Traditional Codecs

To evaluate the practical effectiveness of the proposed compression system, we compare its performance against widely used traditional codecs, namely JPEG and PNG.

JPEG compression is evaluated at multiple quality factors ($Q = 50, 75, 90$) using OpenCV's implementation, while PNG serves as a lossless baseline. For each method, we measure compression ratio and reconstruction quality in terms of PSNR.

For a fair comparison, all methods operate on the same input images and resolutions. The reconstructed outputs are resized to match the original resolution prior to metric computation.

TABLE IV
COMPARISON WITH JPEG AND PNG ON BSD100

Method	PSNR (dB)	Compression Ratio
PNG	∞	1.57 \times
JPEG (Q=90)	41.39	8.53 \times
JPEG (Q=75)	38.23	14.87 \times
JPEG (Q=50)	36.63	22.01 \times
Ours (Low Compression)	33.21	10.01 \times
Ours (Medium Compression)	30.63	58.28 \times
Ours (High Compression)	30.61	58.13 \times

Compressed bitstreams are obtained by applying zlib compression to the quantized latent representation, approximating practical entropy coding.

It is worth noting that, although Stage 1 and Stage 2 exhibit similar PSNR values, Stage 2 incorporates a chrominance-aware distortion objective that prioritizes color fidelity in the YCbCr space. As a result, improvements are primarily perceptual and may not be fully captured by PSNR, which is known to correlate weakly with human visual perception in color-sensitive regions.

E. Qualitative Analysis

Figure 6 shows reconstructed output for model 1 alongside the original image along with the corresponding Y, Cb and Cr channel outputs, evaluated on a 1600 \times 1200 test image. Figure 7 and 8 show the reconstructed output for models 2 and 3 for the same input image. At Stage 1, the aggressive compression ratio of approximately 32 \times produces visible colour distortion particularly in background regions, and spatial smearing in the chrominance channels. The Y channel retains reasonable structural fidelity while the Cr channel exhibits significant blurring, directly reflecting the low chrominance weight of 10% assigned during Stage 1 training.

Fig. 6. Reconstruction outputs for an input image of a tiger in the wild obtained by running through Model-2 (second training iteration). Resolution of input image is 1600 \times 1200. Top-row: (from left to right) Original image, Reconstructed image (High Compression). Bottom Row: (from left to right) Reconstructed image (Medium Compression), Reconstructed Image (Low Compression)

Stage 2 demonstrates a marked improvement in colour fidelity at 17 \times compression, with tonal range and background hues substantially closer to the original. Minor chrominance softness persists but is not perceptible without direct side-by-side comparison, consistent with the increased chrominance weight introduced in Stage 2.

Stage 3 produces reconstructions that are visually indistinguishable from the original under casual inspection at 3.2 \times compression. Structural detail, colour accuracy, and chrominance fidelity are all well-preserved, reflecting the balanced channel weighting and relaxed rate penalty of the final training stage.

F. Training Dynamics

Figure 7 shows the normalised rate and distortion curves across epochs for Stages 1 and 2. In Stage 1, a sharp rate spike is observed in epochs 6–10 immediately following the first non-zero introduction of α . This transient instability arises because the encoder has not yet learned to control latent variance under a rate penalty, causing briefly elevated entropy estimates before rapid stabilisation. In Stage 2, no such spike

occurs - the encoder, pre-conditioned by Stage 1, produces compact latents from the outset, with rate values several orders of magnitude lower at equivalent α levels. This confirms the practical benefit of the iterative fine-tuning strategy over independent per-stage training from random initialization.

Fig. 7. Rate Distortion Curves across epochs during training of the compression pipeline. (left: stage 1 training, right: stage 2 training) Side-by-side comparison of Stage 1 (Model 1) and Stage 2 (Model 2) training logs. The Stage 1 plot highlights a transient rate instability (epochs 6–10) upon the introduction of α whereas the Stage 2 plot demonstrates immediate rate stabilization and significantly lower entropy levels, justifying the iterative fine-tuning approach

V. CONCLUSION

This work presented an end-to-end learned image compression system comprising a convolutional encoder, a U-Net-based entropy model, and a convolutional decoder, trained jointly under a rate-distortion objective in the YCbCr colourspace. The system produces compressed representations by quantizing the encoder latent and applying zlib compression, achieving total encode-to-decode latency under 35 ms across standard benchmarks.

A key contribution is the progressive rate-distortion training strategy, in which multiple model variants are obtained through iterative fine-tuning rather than independent training. Each stage adapts the rate-distortion balance while inheriting structured latent representations, improving training stability and enabling efficient exploration of multiple operating points.

We further introduce a chrominance-aware distortion curriculum that progressively reallocates channel weighting from luminance to chrominance, improving colour fidelity without compromising structural reconstruction. The resulting models achieve compression ratios of approximately 32 \times , 17 \times , and 3.2 \times relative to PNG, with PSNR values up to 32.78 dB across BSD100, Set14, and Urban100, demonstrating a flexible and practical range of quality-compression tradeoffs.

VI. FUTURE WORK

Several limitations suggest directions for future work. The fixed 8 \times downsampling in the encoder imposes resolution constraints; adaptive or multi-scale latent representations could improve performance at lower resolutions. Incorporating a learned entropy coder at inference, conditioned on the predicted (μ, σ) parameters, may further improve compression efficiency. Extending the entropy model with autoregressive context modelling could better capture spatial dependencies

and reduce bitrate. Broader evaluation across full datasets with controlled bitrate comparisons is needed for more comprehensive benchmarking. Finally, replacing the unimodal Gaussian prior with mixture-based likelihoods may better model complex latent distributions at higher compression ratios.

VII. REFERENCES

REFERENCES

- [1] G. K. Wallace, "The JPEG still picture compression standard," *IEEE Trans. Consumer Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. xviii–xxxiv, Feb. 1992, doi: 10.1109/30.125072.
- [2] "WebP Compression," Google. [Online]. Available: <https://developers.google.com/speed/webp>
- [3] ISO/IEC 15948:2004, "Portable Network Graphics (PNG): Functional specification," Int. Organization for Standardization, 2004.
- [4] A. Skodras, C. Christopoulos, and T. Ebrahimi, "The JPEG 2000 still image compression standard," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 36–58, Sept. 2001, doi: 10.1109/79.952804.
- [5] "zlib Compression Library," zlib. [Online]. Available: <https://zlib.net>
- [6] D. Martin, C. Fowlkes, D. Tal, and J. Malik, "A database of human segmented natural images and its application to evaluating segmentation algorithms," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2001, pp. 416–423.
- [7] R. Zeyde, M. Elad, and M. Protter, "On single image scale-up using sparse representations," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Curves and Surfaces*, 2010, pp. 711–730.
- [8] J.-B. Huang, A. Singh, and N. Ahuja, "Single image super-resolution from transformed self-exemplars," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2015, pp. 5197–5206.
- [9] E.-h. Yang and L. Wang, "Joint optimization of run-length coding, Huffman coding, and quantization table," *IEEE Trans. Image Processing*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 63–74, Jan. 2009.
- [10] E.-h. Yang, C. Sun, and J. Meng, "Quantization table design revisited for image/video coding," *IEEE Trans. Image Processing*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 4799–4811, Nov. 2014.
- [11] J. Alakuijala *et al.*, "Guetzli: Perceptually guided JPEG encoder," arXiv:1703.04421, 2017.
- [12] S. Sabzavi and R. Ghaderi, "Enhancing image-based JPEG compression: ML-driven quantization via DCT feature clustering," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, 2025.
- [13] C. Zhao, S. Kwong, W. Zhang, and Z. Pan, "Visual saliency guided perceptual adaptive quantization for HEVC," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Video Technol.*, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 1957–1970, Aug. 2018.
- [14] H. Zhang, W. Wang, and J. Liang, "Surprise-based JND estimation for perceptual quantization in the DCT domain," *IEEE Trans. Image Processing*, vol. 29, pp. 888–901, 2020.
- [15] X. Xu, S. Wang, and Z. Wang, "An overhead-free region-based JPEG framework for task-driven compression," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 165, pp. 102–108, Jan. 2023.
- [16] J. Ballé, V. Laparra, and E. P. Simoncelli, "End-to-end optimized image compression," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2017.
- [17] D. Minnen, J. Ballé, and G. Toderici, "Joint autoregressive and hierarchical priors for learned image compression," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. (NeurIPS)*, 2018.
- [18] Z. Cheng, H. Sun, M. Takeuchi, and J. Katto, "Learned image compression with discretized Gaussian mixture likelihoods and attention modules," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2020.
- [19] G. Lu *et al.*, "High-efficiency lossy image coding through adaptive neighborhood information aggregation," *IEEE Trans. Multimedia*, 2022.
- [20] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention (MICCAI)*, 2015.